

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

ESG APPROACH TO MANAGING ERGONOMIC SCHOOLS

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Abstract

ESG approach is rapidly spreading in business management. The authors extrapolate this approach to the educational system and prove its connection with the provision of ergonomic efficiency of educational organization. It is proved that ESG approach ("environment, social issues, management") in educational organizations requires updating approaches to their management. The ergonomic aspect of ESG principles is considered. It is ergonomics of architecture and design of school environment as an open space; correspondence of educational process to the Goal of sustainable development - providing quality and accessibility of education; ergonomics of educational organization activity in the surrounding socio-natural environment.

Keywords: ESG approach, management, sustainable development, ergonomics.

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The ESG approach, which stands for Environment, Social, Governance, is a strategy for the development of an organization that provides for its management in a way that ensures its economic efficiency, biosphere-compatible functioning, and socio-cultural development to meet the challenges of sustainable development [1]. The ESG approach was first formulated in 2004 by Kofi Annan, the Secretary General of the United Nations. Today the ESG principles have entered into the activities of not only large corporations, but also many small and medium-sized companies. It helps them to attract investments and take high places in ESG rankings [2]. ESG approach could be attractive for education as well. It could allow organizing and carrying out effective, conscious management of an educational organization, its transformation into an innovative structure providing modernization of education, its high and competitive quality [3].

The implementation of ESG requires a fundamentally new approach to management from the head of a general education organization. The school management model should be able to respond to the existing challenges and emerging trends in social development, scientifically justify the ongoing transformations in the school organization, increase and flexibly regulate the resources of sustainable development.

School leaders, as never before, need scientific management developments capable of solving these problems. At the same time, it seems to us that today it

is practically impossible to achieve maximum efficiency in managing the development of the education system only at the expense of its internal connections and resources. The school is an organic part of the educational socio-cultural space; an object of influence of socio-economic, natural, cultural conditions of society life; a part of social organism, subordinated in its development to one whole. Management of sustainable development of educational organization is a pedagogically organized process on the basis of its public orientation to achieve social partnership, productive solution of socially significant problems, when all stakeholders have the opportunity to participate in decision-making, guided by the same principles and values of sustainable development [4;5]. Such management provides specially organized joint activity of all participants of processes, their communication, systematic interaction of school with civil, state and business structures of society. Managing a modern school requires understanding, discovering, studying as many connections and relations between individual and collective subjects of management as possible and relying on these connections in work. Such connections are integrative, system-forming, providing integrity of managing system and its development [6].

Thus, the focus on the ESG approach stimulates the school's search for models of management as a territory of sustainable development. However, applying only the pedagogical approach to solve such a complex problem seems insufficient. It cannot pretend to the completeness and integrity of solutions and requires an exit to interdisciplinary social mechanisms of management. The basic component of social mechanisms of management is social partnership. In ESG mode, it becomes an important condition for implementing the socio-natural expediency of school functioning, modeling education management as an ecosystem, solving the

humanistic problem of optimizing the educational process and students' development. In the interdisciplinary approach to solving these tasks of the school of sustainable development an important role is played by the ergonomic component present in all areas of school activity - in the organization of the educational space, the educational process, the interaction of the school with the society [7].

Principles of school life ergonomics: efficiency; effectiveness; optimality; relationship of educational space ergonomics and educational process ergonomics; rationality; safety; culture of educational and pedagogical work; program-target planning - according to the scheme "goals - ways - means"; humanism; common purpose of participants and cooperation; openness; consistency; anticipatory nature; future-oriented; mobility; flexibility; feedback [8].

The principles of ergonomic management: accountability and transparency; universal participation; response to social needs; mutual assistance, mutual responsibility and universal desire to implement the goals set; reliance on traditional national values, cultural heritage and modern science; anticipatory, predictive nature; use of digital and networking capabilities; giving the school units and teachers responsible autonomy within their competence;

facilitating the processes of creative self-realization of partnership subjects through supporting a variety of initiatives within the school, encouraging the continuous professional development of teachers and other specialists; ensuring the continuity, permanence, continuity of the process of sustainable school development in conditions of interagency cooperation as a strategic direction;

using the cultural and educational potential of the environment; implementation of training content on the methodology of interdisciplinarity, taking into account the characteristics, problems, the mission of the school [9].

Ergonomic educational process means continuity of value and worldview ideas of sustainable development; orientation on achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals; integrated activity of school and partners (general education, secondary education, higher education institutions, postgraduate, additional education of children and adults, institutions of science, culture, sports...) to solve problems of mutual interest of education and region, taking into account strategic tasks of socio-economic development; inclusion of ergonomics issues in content of education and its n

The school building itself as a resource of ESD becomes a subject of study, makes it possible to solve many problems of ESD not through introduction of special lessons or courses, but through demonstration to children the features of functioning of the building, acquaintance with modern technologies of management of the school as an organization. According to N. Karyakina, a resource for ESD is a building which can tell schoolchildren about its load on the environment through a system of inscriptions near electric switches, taps, and batteries. It can show the administration's concern for environmental problems by familiarizing students with the plan for spending money on repairs: what

the money is for, what the priorities are, and why they are arranged in this way.

Ergonomic school building can be the subject of a large number of individual and group projects of schoolchildren, ensure the involvement of students in productive communication and activity: group, dialog forms of work in the classroom, club forms of work in extracurricular activities and in additional education [11].

Green ergonomic building will be not only a visual aid. It saves resources, preserves health and the environment. The ergonomic development of a green school is its aim to meet the real needs of both all subjects of education and the population of a particular region as widely as possible.

The implementation of ESG approach to the management of a "green" school requires the development of a system of "quality indicators" of education for sustainable development. Based on the UNESCO recommendations, SD goals, the following indicators can be considered.

Indicators of actions 1. information about social partnership activities 1.1. its regulatory and legal framework 1.2. connection with the Sustainable Development Goals of the local community, region Indicators of ESD 2.1. inclusion of sustainable development topics in the content of education. 2.2. reflection of its meanings and values in the content General institutional approach to ESD 2.3. 2.4. Pedagogical criteria and indicators. 2.5. education for sustainable development Indicator: qualifications of educators.

Indicators such as teacher readiness are added: 3.1. Inclusion of ESD in teacher training frameworks. 3.2. Opportunities for teachers to collaborate in EI Indicator: Educational environment 4.1. Availability of teaching tools and teaching aids on ESD. 4.2. Availability of teaching materials and methodological aids on ESD. Development of social effect indicators.

Conclusion. The ESG approach can be effective not only in business, but also in education. It allows connecting ideas of school ergonomics with its function of socio-cultural center of sustainable development of local community on the level of management.

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Abstract

This article, as long-term experience shows, examines the work of many sports organizations and firms, the work on successful business under a certain set of conditions. One of such important conditions is the qualified management of a sports organization based on the constant collection and analysis of information about target markets and consumers, followed by adjustments in terms of personnel, marketing, advertising and other policies. In the article we report that physical culture and sport are closely related to such concepts as management, marketing, advertising, pricing, business planning and economics in general.

It is also noted that in recent decades, the industry of physical culture, sports and tourism has been rapidly developing as a broad sphere of entrepreneurial activity.